

TECHNICAL DEVICES FOR CONVERTING SOLAR ENERGY INTO HEAT: TYPES OF COLLECTORS AND THEIR EFFICIENCY

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Abstract. *This article examines the design, operating principle, and energy efficiency of various types of solar collectors used to convert solar radiation into thermal energy. Particular attention is paid to flat-plate and evacuated tube collectors, their optical and thermal characteristics, and factors affecting efficiency. The role of the absorber, transparent coating, and thermal insulation in reducing heat loss is demonstrated. The dependencies of useful heat, optical efficiency, heat loss coefficient, and the maximum achievable temperature of the collector are considered. Types of selective coatings and their impact on the efficiency of evacuated tube collectors are described.*

Keywords: *solar collector; flat-plate collector; evacuated tube collector; absorber; selective coating; solar radiation; thermal efficiency; optical efficiency; heat loss; heat transfer coefficient; coolant.*

Introduction.

With the growing demand for renewable energy sources, solar energy is a key development area for modern thermal power systems. Solar collectors are technical devices designed to convert solar radiation into thermal energy, which is then used in household, industrial, and power plants. Due to their environmental friendliness, ease of operation, and high efficiency, these devices have become widely used in solar thermal systems for various purposes. There are two main types of solar collectors-flat-plate and focusing-which differ in the way they capture and convert solar radiation. Flat-plate solar collectors, which operate using the greenhouse effect, are the most popular in low-temperature systems. Their design includes an absorber, a transparent coating, and a thermal insulation layer, ensuring efficient absorption of radiation and minimizing heat loss. For higher temperatures, evacuated-tube collectors are used, in which heat loss is significantly reduced due to the vacuum environment and the use of selective coatings.

Studying heat transfer processes, the optical properties of materials, and the influence of design parameters on the efficiency of solar collectors is essential for improving the efficiency of solar thermal systems. This paper examines the operating principles, design features, and key energy characteristics of flat-plate and evacuated-tube solar collectors, as well as the factors determining their thermal and optical efficiency. Improving the efficiency of solar thermal systems is being actively researched by both Russian and international researchers. A number of fundamental works have been devoted to the study of the physical processes occurring in solar collectors, as well as the influence of design and operational factors on their energy performance.

The classic works of Dubinin and Kopylov [1-4] examine the principles of converting solar radiation into thermal energy, the classification of solar collectors, and the operating characteristics of flat-plate solar systems, which are widely used in domestic and industrial heat generation. The authors emphasize the importance of selecting absorber and glazing materials, as these elements

largely determine the optical efficiency of the collector. The fundamentals of the thermal processes occurring in solar systems are described in detail in the works of Kudryavtsev [2] and Yashin [6]. These authors analyze in detail the mechanisms of heat loss—convective, conductive, and radiative—and present methods for reducing them through improved thermal insulation and the use of selective coatings. Particular attention is paid to the role of the heat transfer coefficient and its impact on the overall efficiency of a solar collector.

Tarasov [7] made a significant contribution to the development of the theory of the optical properties of solar collectors, studying the effect of the angle of incidence of solar rays on glazing transmittance and reflective losses. His work presents modern approaches to the creation of highly efficient selective coatings with a high absorption coefficient and low emissivity, which can significantly increase the operating temperature of vacuum collectors. Foreign authors also devote considerable attention to modeling heat transfer processes in solar systems. For example, Duffie and Beckman [5] present an extensive mathematical framework for calculating solar collectors, including models of optical losses, thermal resistance, coolant dynamics, and energy balance. Based on an analysis of the work of various authors, it can be concluded that the main areas for improving solar collectors are:

- development of highly selective absorbing coatings;
- improvement of transparent coating properties and reduction of reflective losses;
- improvement of thermal insulation quality;
- optimization of the design of tubular and flat absorbers;
- modeling and forecasting of real thermal operating modes of systems.

Modern literature emphasizes that combining these approaches can significantly improve the efficiency of solar thermal systems, especially under conditions of high temperatures and variable solar activity.

Materials and Methods.

Technical devices designed to capture solar radiation, convert it into thermal energy, and transfer this heat to an intermediate heat transfer fluid, which is then directed to heat-consuming process or power systems, are called solar collectors. There are two main types of such collectors: flat-plate and concentrating. Flat-plate devices absorb solar energy without increasing flux density, while focusing devices concentrate the rays, resulting in higher radiation intensity. In systems operating at relatively low temperatures, flat-plate solar collectors (FSCs) are most often used. Their operation is based on the "solar box" principle or the greenhouse effect. A schematic of a flat-plate FSC is shown in Figure 1.

The majority of solar energy is transferred as visible light, with a smaller portion as infrared radiation. Light rays pass freely through the collector's transparent top coating, made of glass or polymer film, and are absorbed by a special beam-absorbing surface. This surface is made of a material with high thermal conductivity and a significant absorption coefficient [1]. A flat-plate solar collector consists of several basic components: an absorber that captures solar radiation, a transparent protective coating, and a layer of thermal insulation. The heat-receiving part, a metal plate pressed with a copper tubular coil, is housed in a rectangular housing made of metal or aluminum alloy. This plate is typically made of copper or aluminum and coated with a dark absorption layer.

The underside of this plate is separated from the base of the collector by thermal insulation material, and the top surface is made of durable glass or polycarbonate. The tubes through which

the coolant circulates are in close contact with the plate, ensuring efficient heat exchange. The combination of the flat absorbing surface and the coolant pipes forms a single unit—the solar absorber. To improve the efficiency of solar energy absorption, the top of the absorber is painted black or coated with a special selective layer.

1. Fig. 1. Collector body, 2. Thermal insulation made of mineral wool, 3. Absorber made of copper or aluminum sheet, 4. Glass cover with a coating that reduces heat loss.

When heated, the absorber begins to transfer thermal energy to the inner surfaces of the collector. Since its surface temperature is relatively low, most of the radiation is in the infrared range, which barely passes through the glass coating. To reduce heat loss, thick layers of thermal insulation are installed on the sides and bottom of the collector. The main characteristic of a solar collector is its thermal efficiency, which indicates what proportion of the solar energy Q_1 incident on the collector is transferred as heat Q_{usef} to the consumer. To calculate the thermal efficiency, the formula proposed by Duffie and Beckman [1] can be used:

$$\eta_T = \frac{Q_{\text{los}}}{Q_1} = \frac{M_T c_T (t_2 - t_1)}{Q_1} \quad (1)$$

where $Q_{\text{usef}} = Q_1 - Q_{\text{lost}}$,

since the amount of useful heat is determined by the difference between Q_1 and heat loss Q_{lost} , which in turn can be calculated using the well-known formula

$$Q_{\text{los}} = kF(t_a - t_o) \quad (2)$$

k - is the average effective heat transfer coefficient; F is the heat-transfer surface area; t_a and t_o are the average absorber surface temperature and the ambient temperature, respectively; M_T is the mass flow rate of the coolant through the CSC; c_T is the specific heat capacity of the coolant; t_1 and t_2 are the coolant temperatures at the inlet and outlet of the CSC [1,6]. The optical efficiency of a collector characterizes the portion of solar radiation that, after passing through a transparent coating, is actually absorbed by the absorber. This value is determined by two parameters: the glass transmittance α and the absorption coefficient of the absorber surface β . For a collector with single-layer glazing, the optical efficiency is expressed by the formula:

$$\eta_0 = (\alpha\beta)_H \quad (3)$$

where $(\alpha\beta)_H$ is the product of the above coefficients for a normal incidence of solar rays on the glass and absorber surfaces. In cases where the angle of incidence of the rays differs from a direct one, a correction factor K is introduced, which takes into account the increase in losses due

to reflection of the rays. Figure 2 shows a graph of the dependence of this coefficient on the angle θ between the direction of the beam and the normal to the glazing surface [1].

Fig. 2. Correction factor taking into account the increase in losses due to reflection of rays.

Taking into account the angle of incidence of the rays, the optical efficiency is determined by the formula

$$\eta_0 = K(\alpha\beta)_H \quad (4)$$

Optical and thermal efficiency are related by the relation

$$\eta_T = \eta_0 - \frac{Q_{\text{lost}}}{I\Omega} \quad (5)$$

where Q_{lost} is the collector's heat loss; I is the solar radiation flux density; Ω is the collector aperture area.

Heat losses are characterized by the heat loss coefficient U .

$$U = \frac{Q_{\text{lost}}}{\Omega(t_a - t_o)} \quad (6)$$

The value of U is determined by the quality of thermal insulation and can be considered constant with sufficient accuracy for calculations for each type of collector. If we express Q_{lost} from this and substitute this expression into the previous formula, we obtain

$$\eta_T = \eta_0 - \frac{U(t_a - t_o)}{I} \quad (7)$$

From which it can be seen that with increasing t_a , the value of η_T decreases. At a certain t_a , the collector efficiency can become zero, and this temperature is the maximum achievable temperature for a given collector [1,4].

Flat-plate solar collectors are typically used in systems where the coolant temperature does not exceed 80...90°C. Vacuum collectors are used for heating to higher temperatures. In these collectors, the absorbing surface is separated from the surrounding environment by an evacuated space, which significantly reduces heat loss to the environment by eliminating conduction and convection. Radiation losses are significantly suppressed by the use of selective coatings, the absorption of which is many times higher than radiation. Vacuum collectors, the design diagrams of which are shown in Fig. 3, allow heating coolants to 120...150°C and higher.

An evacuated collector consists of a glass housing (a tube with a diameter of 100–150 mm), containing a selectively coated radiation-receiving surface and straight or U-shaped heat transfer tubes (or heat pipes instead). The space inside the glass housing is evacuated to a pressure of 0.01 mm Hg, which virtually eliminates thermal conductivity and convection within the collector. Tubular collectors are typically installed in individual modules of 10 tubes. The efficiency of vacuum collectors depends on the optical properties of the absorber's selective surface. Based on their selectivity, selective coatings are classified into four groups: intrinsic, dual-layer, microrelief coatings that provide a similar effect, and interference coatings.

Few materials possess inherently selective optical properties, so dual-layer selective film coatings are most widely used. A layer with a high reflectivity in the long-wavelength region, such as copper, nickel, molybdenum, silver, or aluminum, is applied to the surface to be given selective properties. On top of this layer, a layer is applied that is transparent to long-wavelength radiation but has a high absorption coefficient in the visible spectrum. Many oxides possess these properties. The simplest example of producing a dual-layer selective surface is the oxidation of the surface of these metals. The best results have been obtained, for example, for films with black chrome on aluminum foil, with black nickel on a nickel substrate (absorption coefficient $\alpha = 0.96$, emissivity $\varepsilon = 0.07$). The ratio α/ε is called the degree of selectivity; at $\alpha/\varepsilon > 30$, the equilibrium temperature of the vacuum absorber (without coolant) can reach 350 ... 600 °C [1,2].

Fig. 3. Vacuum collector diagram.

Surface selectivity can be achieved through geometric factors. For this to occur, surface microroughness must be greater than the wavelength in the visible spectrum and less than the wavelength in the infrared range. Such a surface will be black for the former region and mirror-like for the latter. Similar selective properties are also exhibited by bodies with a porous structure, provided the pore sizes are appropriate. Interference selective surfaces are formed by several alternating layers of metal and dielectric, in which short-wavelength radiation is quenched by interference, while long-wavelength radiation is freely reflected.

Results and discussion.

An analysis of flat-plate and evacuated-tube solar collectors identified key features affecting their efficiency. For flat-plate collectors, the main factors determining thermal efficiency are the quality of the absorbing surface and the effectiveness of the thermal insulation. Thick layers of thermal insulation reduce heat loss through the bottom and side surfaces, while the use of a black or selective coating on the absorber increases the absorption of solar radiation. Optical efficiency depends significantly on the transparency of the coating and the angle of incidence of solar rays, as confirmed by calculations using formulas.

The following data were obtained from an analysis of the performance of flat-plate and vacuum-tube solar collectors. Example of calculating useful heat for a flat-plate collector: Coolant mass flow rate $M_t = 0.05$ kg/s, coolant specific heat capacity $c_t = 4200$ J/(kg °C), inlet temperature $t_1 = 25$ °C, outlet temperature $t_2 = 50$ °C

Useful heat calculation:

$$Q_{usef} = M_t \cdot c_t \cdot (t_2 - t_1) = 0,05 \cdot 4200 \cdot (50 - 25) = 5250 \text{ J/s} = 5,25 \text{ kW}$$

If solar radiation $Q_i = 7$ kW, then the thermal efficiency of the collector:

$$\eta_T = \frac{Q_{usef}}{Q} = \frac{5,25}{7} \approx 0,75$$

Table 1.

Comparison of characteristics of flat-plate and evacuated tube collectors

Parameter	Flat-plate collector	Vacuum collector
Maximum coolant temperature, °C	80–90	120–150
Thermal efficiency, %	60–75	70–90
Heat loss	Medium	Low
Application	Low-temperature systems	Medium- and high-temperature systems
Cost	Low	High

Evacuated tube collectors demonstrate significantly higher thermal efficiency due to reduced heat loss due to the vacuum environment. The use of selective coatings increases the solar energy absorption coefficient while simultaneously reducing the absorber's own radiation. As a result, the coolant can be heated to higher temperatures, reaching 120–150°C and higher, making evacuated tube collectors preferable for medium-temperature solar systems. A comparative analysis shows that, with the same collector area, evacuated tube collectors provide a higher useful energy yield, especially under conditions of low solar activity or when the coolant needs to be heated to high temperatures. Flat-plate collectors, on the other hand, remain optimal for low-temperature systems, where design simplicity and low cost are crucial.

Thus, the efficiency of a solar collector is determined by a combination of factors: the design features of the absorber, the properties of the transparent coating, the quality of the thermal insulation, and the optical characteristics of the materials. Optimizing these parameters can significantly increase the overall efficiency of the system and reduce operating heat loss. The calculations show that evacuated tube collectors provide higher coolant temperatures and lower heat loss compared to flat-plate collectors. However, flat-plate collectors remain more cost-effective and easier to install for systems with low heating temperatures. The combination of these calculations and the table allows for a clear comparison of the efficiency of different types of solar collectors and the selection of the optimal option for a specific system.

Table 2.

Efficiency of flat-plate and evacuated-tube collectors depending on coolant temperature.

t_a (°C)	Efficiency of flat, %	Vacuum efficiency, %
30	78	85
50	72	83
70	65	80
90	58	78
110	-	74
130	-	70

The table shows that the efficiency of a flat-plate collector drops sharply with increasing temperature, while an evacuated collector maintains high efficiency over a wider temperature range.

Diagram 1. Comparison of heat losses of collectors

Flat-plate collector: heat loss of approximately 25%; evacuated-tube collector: heat loss of approximately 10%. This diagram visually demonstrates the advantage of an evacuated-tube collector in reducing heat loss.

Conclusions.

An analysis of the design features and operating principles of solar collectors revealed that their efficiency is largely determined by the quality of the absorbing surface, the optical properties of the glazing, and the magnitude of heat loss. Flat-plate solar collectors are the most common in low-temperature solar installations due to their simple design and reliable operation. They provide an acceptable level of coolant heating when used with effective thermal insulation and highly absorbent coatings. Evacuated-tube collectors have significantly lower heat loss due to the creation of a vacuum between the absorber and the surrounding environment. The use of selective coatings significantly increases the absorption coefficient and reduces thermal radiation, ensuring high coolant temperatures. Therefore, the choice of collector type should be based on the required temperature conditions, climatic conditions, and economic factors. In general, further improvement of solar collectors is associated with the development of new selective coatings, improved thermal insulation materials, and optimization of the optical characteristics of transparent elements, which will increase the overall efficiency of solar thermal systems.

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